

PARTICIPATION OF GENERATION Z BEGINNER VOTERS IN THE 2024 PRESIDENTIAL AND VICE PRESIDENTIAL ELECTIONS IN BANDUNG CITY

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ABSTRACT

This study is the participation of generation z beginner voters in the 2024 presidential and vice presidential elections in Bandung City. This study aims to determine how Generation Z's political participation is in Bandung City and to determine what factors support and inhibit Generation Z's participation in the 2024 elections in Bandung City. This study uses a descriptive method using the theoretical concept from Meriam Budiardjo's book regarding awareness and belief in political participation. The data collected came from direct interviews with informants in accordance with the title of the study, the data obtained was reduced and verified. The results of this study found that Generation Z's political participation in the 2024 elections in Bandung City was quite good even though the level of participation in the 2024 elections fell to 82% when compared to the 2019 elections of 86%. In addition, there are factors that support and inhibit Generation Z's political participation in Bandung City, factors that support Generation Z's political participation in Bandung City are Generation Z's awareness of politics that can determine the next candidate for the country's leader. While the factors that inhibit Generation Z's political participation in Bandung City are due to the lack of election socialization to the community and there is still money politics. So that the socialization regarding political education carried out by the KPU and political parties has less impact on the basic election process.

Keywords: Political Participation, Generation Z, 2024 Elections, Bandung City

INTRODUCTION

General elections (Pemilu) are the main foundation in the democratic system, which represents the sovereignty of the people as stated in Article 1 Paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution. One indicator of the success of the implementation of democracy in Indonesia is the increase in public participation in elections, especially from the group of first-time voters. In the context of the 2024 Presidential and Vice Presidential Elections, Generation Z – namely individuals born in the mid-1990s to

the early 2010s – is a strategic group because demographically they dominate the proportion of young voters.

In general, the right to vote is generally a form of political participation that reflects the sovereignty of the people manifested in the general election process, through direct voting, playing the most influential role in the political dynamics of a region. First-time voters have a significant role in elections, but they are often considered less experienced because they have never adapted to previous elections, the various challenges faced such as lack of experience among first-time voters often lead to a lack of concern for the democratic system, especially in the upcoming 2024 elections. This is a major challenge, especially for Generation Z who have lost attention to the existence of the electoral system. Therefore, there are several approaches that must be used to make the Young Generation, especially Generation Z as first-time voters, continue to care and participate in the democratic system, namely by participating in general elections.

The General Elections Commission (KPU) is tasked with increasing the engagement of first-time voters, particularly Generation Z, which includes individuals born between the mid-1990s and the early 2010s. Generation Z is a rapidly growing group amidst technological and information developments. Therefore, to encourage their participation in elections, the approach used must be tailored to their preferences, characteristics, and strategies. One approach that the General Elections Commission can implement to encourage Generation Z to participate in elections is by utilizing technological advances to convey information on social media through relevant and engaging content that this election is very important and is their right and responsibility as voters and citizens of Indonesia.

Generation Z has fast and broad access to information that influences how they understand and evaluate presidential candidates and related issues. Social media is a major factor in shaping their political views. However, other aspects such as educational background, social environment, and participation in organizations can also influence their political preferences. Nevertheless, many parties, including political parties, academics, and political observers, still question Generation Z's voting patterns. Generation Z now relies on social media as a primary source for accessing information, participating in discussions, and expressing their views on various political issues. The influence of social media can be seen in how these platforms shape adolescents' political preferences, from the process of opinion formation, the occurrence of polarization, to the emergence of the filter bubble effect that causes adolescents to be more frequently exposed to views that align with their own.

Researching Generation Z's political engagement is interesting, especially considering the role of social media in building political awareness among teenagers. With widespread access and the ability to disseminate information instantly and quickly, social media plays a crucial role in various political processes. Understanding the characteristics and values held by Generation Z, such as their

reliance on technology and social media, is key to understanding their engagement patterns. Social media has become the primary platform for Generation Z to obtain information, engage in discussions, and voice their opinions on political issues.

However, Generation Z participation still faces several challenges, including low political literacy, minimal outreach from election organizers, and the negative influence of social media and vote buying practices. A 2022 CSIS survey showed that social media is a primary source of information for Generation Z, but it is also a breeding ground for the spread of biased information and the polarization of political opinion. Generation Z participation is important not only in terms of quantity but also the quality of democracy itself. Therefore, understanding the forms, motivations, and factors that inhibit and encourage political participation by this group is crucial. Moreover, low political participation among the younger generation can impact the quality of election legitimacy and potentially undermine democratic integrity in the long term.

Sumber Informasi Pemilih Muda

Gambar 1. Source of information for young voters (Source: Hasil Survei CSIS 2022)

Generation Z now relies on social media as a primary source for accessing information, participating in discussions, and expressing their views on various political issues. The influence of social media can be seen in how these platforms shape adolescents' political preferences, from the process of opinion formation and polarization to the emergence of the filter bubble effect, which causes adolescents to be more frequently exposed to views that align with their own. However, the use of social media to raise political awareness is not without challenges, such as issues of trust in circulating information and the tendency for opinion polarization. Nevertheless, these challenges can also be seen as opportunities to strengthen engagement and increase political participation among adolescents more broadly.

Generation Z has rapid and widespread access to information, influencing how they understand and evaluate presidential candidates and related issues. Social

media is a major factor shaping their political views. However, other aspects such as educational background, social environment, and participation in organizations can also influence their political preferences. This participation not only enhances their understanding of the election process but also fosters a sense of moral responsibility for the integrity of democracy. Thus, Generation Z is expected to not only become active voters but also act as agents of change, positively impacting the political process and safeguarding democracy. Participatory monitoring also provides an opportunity for Generation Z to learn more about elections, applicable regulations, and potential violations. The 2024 election will be a crucial moment for Indonesia, especially as many Generation Z will be voters for the first time. Therefore, efforts to increase their political involvement should be a priority, and participatory monitoring is a crucial strategy to encourage this generation to be more active in maintaining the quality of democracy.

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The problematic phenomena that occur in increasing the participation of Generation Z first-time voters in Bandung City include low political awareness and limited access to information, problems faced include the uneven influence of social media and the lack of effective strategies in reaching and involving them in the election process, this shows that there is a mismatch between the potential for participation and the reality that occurs in the 2024 election in Bandung City. This study focuses on Bandung City, which in the previous election (2019) recorded a fairly high participation rate, namely 86%. However, in the 2024 Election, the participation rate decreased to 82%. This decline needs to be analyzed in depth, especially regarding the contribution and involvement of first-time voters from Generation Z.

The hope is that Generation Z can become more aware of participating if they want to see and follow the development of good elections in the election of heads of government, currently the role of Generation Z in the political circle must be increasingly noticed, both in Indonesia and throughout the world. Political elites approach first-time voters in various ways during the election campaign, because Generation Z plays an important role in the election, because they are one of the

groups that make a large contribution to the level of participation with the existing numbers it is not impossible for political elites to approach first-time voters to choose the candidate pairs they support and this becomes a fierce battle to get their votes and win seats of power.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. The qualitative approach was chosen because this study aims to understand and describe in depth the political participation of Generation Z in the 2024 presidential and vice-presidential elections in Bandung City.

Data Collection Techniques are data sources. Data in this study were collected from two main sources: primary data collected through in-depth interviews with predetermined informants and secondary data collected from related documents, such as research reports, scientific articles, and mass media news. In-depth interviews will be conducted with informants to obtain information regarding their understanding and interpretation of the 2024 elections in Bandung City. Factors influencing voter participation, especially among Generation Z, challenges and obstacles in increasing voter participation, especially among Generation Z, in the 2024 elections. Strategies and recommendations for increasing voter participation. Observations will be conducted to directly observe conditions during the 2024 elections in Bandung City, as well as the activities of the community and related parties during the election.

The collected data will be processed and analyzed qualitatively. The data analysis phase includes data validity testing to ensure the validity and reliability of the information. Data from interviews and observations will be collected and systematically managed. Relevant data will be selected and sorted, while irrelevant data will be discarded. The reduced data will be presented in descriptive narrative form, tables, or charts. Conclusions will be drawn based on the data analysis.

This research will be conducted in Bandung City, focusing on several voters, particularly Generation Z, who are representative of various areas of the city. The research will last for [duration required], from preparation and data collection to data analysis and writing the research report. Use data triangulation (e.g., data source triangulation and method triangulation) to enhance the validity of the research. Observe research ethics, such as informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality of informant data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to describe and analyze how Generation Z will participate in the 2024 presidential and vice-presidential elections in Bandung City. By using Meriam Budiardjo's theory (2007:367) which emphasizes several forms of political participation, namely Conventional Participation and Non-Conventional Participation as a guideline to help researchers describe and also analyze how

Generation Z First-Time Voters Participate in the 2024 Presidential Election in Bandung City.

1. Conventional Participation

Conventional participation is a form of political involvement conducted legally and in accordance with procedures established by the political system. Political participation is an important indicator in assessing the quality of democracy, especially when involving first-time voters like Generation Z. The political participation of Generation Z in Bandung City in the 2024 Presidential and Vice-Presidential Elections shows a strong tendency toward conventional participation patterns; this generation tends to choose to engage through the formal mechanisms provided by the electoral democracy system.

These results reflect that the majority of them possess sufficient political awareness and recognize the importance of participating in the electoral process as part of their civic responsibilities. The level of conventional participation among Generation Z also indicates trust in the election process and institutions. Although not entirely based on in-depth political understanding, this involvement demonstrates an initial commitment to the democratic system. This participation is reinforced by social influences such as education, family, and access to information through digital media, which indirectly shape this generation's political attitudes in the face of the general election.

2. Non Conventional Participation

Non-conventional participation encompasses forms of political engagement that take place outside of official procedures or do not follow institutional channels. This form of participation typically takes the form of protests, petitions, demonstrations, or even more extreme actions such as boycotts or political violence. Non-conventional forms of participation were not significantly visible in the context of the 2024 elections in Bandung. Generation Z prefers to channel their political expression through formal channels, and their involvement in activities outside of legitimate mechanisms was not observed. This indicates that they still trust the existing democratic process and do not see the need for formal or confrontational forms of resistance or political pressure.

This situation also reflects that the political situation in Bandung, particularly regarding the implementation of elections, remains relatively stable and can accommodate the aspirations of the younger generation without triggering unrest that demands action outside the system. However, it also serves as a reminder that formal channels need to be continuously strengthened and trusted so that the younger generation continues to feel that their involvement has a real impact on the political process.

CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that the political participation of Generation Z as first-time voters in the 2024 Presidential and Vice Presidential Election in Bandung City is generally considered quite good. Their involvement is dominated by conventional political participation, reflecting a level of compliance with the prevailing democratic systems and mechanisms. Although this participation does not yet fully reflect critical and substantive political engagement, this finding confirms an initial awareness of the important role of citizens, especially the people of Bandung City, in the general election process. No indication of non-conventional participation was found in the context of this study, indicating that the community, especially Generation Z in Bandung City, tends to channel their political aspirations through official and formal channels. This can be interpreted as a form of trust in the existing political system, but also indicates that their political participation is still procedural and has not yet developed into reflective participation. Factors supporting Generation Z's political participation include political awareness, the influence of the educational and family environment, and the use of social media as a source of information. Conversely, their participation is also hampered by a lack of election socialization, limited understanding of candidates' programs and visions, and the ongoing practice of money politics.

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